

ENHANCING CYBERSECURITY: OPTIMAL ENSEMBLE LEARNING FOR AUTOMATED ANDROID MALWARE DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

Current technological advancement in computer systems has transformed the lives of humans from real to virtual environments. Malware is unnecessary software that is often utilized to launch cyberattacks. Malware variants are still evolving by using advanced packing and obfuscation methods. These approaches make malware classification and detection more challenging. New techniques that are different from conventional systems should be utilized for effectively combating new malware variants. Machine learning (ML) methods are ineffective in identifying all complex and new malware variants. The deep learning (DL) method can be a promising solution to detect all malware variants. This paper presents an Automated Android Malware Detection using Optimal Ensemble Learning Approach for Cybersecurity (AAMD-OELAC) technique. The major aim of the AAMD-OELAC technique lies in the automated classification and identification of Android malware. To achieve this, the AAMD-OELAC technique performs data preprocessing at the preliminary stage. For the Android malware detection process, the AAMD-OELAC technique follows an ensemble learning process using three ML models, namely Least Square Support Vector Machine (LS-SVM),

kernel extreme learning machine (KELM), and Regularized random vector functional link neural network (RRVFLN). Finally, the hunter-prey optimization (HPO) approach is exploited for the optimal parameter tuning of the three DL models, and it helps accomplish improved malware detection results. To denote the supremacy of the AAMD-OELAC method, a comprehensive experimental analysis is conducted. The simulation results portrayed the supremacy of the AAMD-OELAC technique over other existing approaches.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cyber security is becoming a main area of immediate concern to network engineers and computer scientists, so satisfying solutions to several problems are in order [1]. Consequently, the fast technological developments and their inherent integrations in every aspect of lifestyles, various malware apps, and targets become well-identified and studied [2]. Android malware is the malware variety that gained significant interest in the web world. One common operating system is Android, which dominates the operating system market [3].

Malware invasive methods emerge for avoiding identification, as few malware applications have more than 50 parameters

that make detection a difficult one [4]. Hence, it is essential to devise techniques that deal with the continuous growth of Android malware to find it, deactivate or remove it efficiently. All these difficulties engage scholars in the area and urge them to continue more research to find malware and manage it properly [5]. Thus, researchers have developed three mechanisms to find Android malware such as dynamic, static, and hybrid analysis methods. Static analysis extracts the features that assist in identifying harmful performance for apps without a demanding actual application deployment [6]. But this kind of analysis suffered from code obfuscation methods which assist help malware author to avoid static methods. Dynamic analysis can be used for determining the malware of apps in their runtime [7]. Commonly, the static analysis feature offers the capability of locating the malware element using source code, while the dynamic analysis feature offers the capability of finding the location of malware in a runtime environment. Android developers and users can be exposed to unnecessary risks and dangers with malware [8]. This study covers malware detection methods. The detection of malware using the ML model includes Android Application Packages (APKs) for deriving an appropriate set of features. Deep learning (DL) and machine learning (ML) approaches can be used for recognizing malicious APKs [9]. Like malware detection, vulnerability detection in software code has two stages: training ML on derived attributes to find vulnerable code segments and feature generation utilizing code analysis [10].

This paper presents an Automated Android Malware Detection using Optimal Ensemble Learning Approach for Cyber security (AAMD-OELAC) technique. The AAMDOELAC technique performs data preprocessing at the preliminary stage. For the Android malware detection process, the AAMD-OELAC technique follows an ensemble learning process using three ML models, namely Least Square Support Vector Machine (LS-SVM), kernel extreme learning machine (KELM), and Regularized random vector functional link neural network (RRVFLN). Finally, the hunter-prey optimization (HPO) algorithm is exploited for the optimal parameter tuning of the three DL models, and it helps accomplish improved malware detection results. To indicate the supremacy of the AAMD-OELAC approach, a comprehensive experimental analysis is carried out. In short, the key contributions are listed as follows.

- An intelligent AAMD-OELAC technique comprising data preprocessing, ensemble learning, and HPO-based hyper parameter tuning is presented for Android malware detection. To the best of our knowledge, the AAMD-OELAC technique never existed in the literature.

- Perform ensemble learning-based classification process comprising LS-SVM, KELM, and RRVFLN models for Android malware detection.

- The combination of the HPO algorithm and ensemble learning process improves the detection accuracy of Android malware. By utilizing multiple classifiers and optimization strategies, the model can

effectively identify malicious patterns and behaviors in Android applications.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

“Adversarial superiority in Android malware detection: Lessons from reinforcement learning based evasion attacks and defenses,”

Today, android smartphones are being used by billions of users and thus have become a lucrative target of malware designers. Therefore being one step ahead in this zero-sum game of malware detection between the anti-malware community and malware developers is more of a necessity than a desire. This work focuses on a proactive adversary-aware framework to develop adversarially superior android malware detection models. We first investigate the adversarial robustness of thirty-six distinct malware detection models constructed using two static features (permission and intent) and eighteen classification algorithms. We designed two Targeted Type-II Evasion Attacks (*TRPO-MalEAttack* and *PPO-MalEAttack*) based on reinforcement learning to exploit vulnerabilities in the above malware detection models. The attacks aim to add minimum perturbations in each malware application and convert it into an adversarial application that can fool the malware detection models. The *TRPO-MalEAttack* achieves an average fooling rate of 95.75% (with 2.02 mean perturbations), reducing the average accuracy from 86.01% to 49.11% in thirty-six malware detection models. On the other hand, The *PPO-MalEAttack* achieves a higher average fooling rate of 96.87% (with

2.08 mean perturbations), reducing the average accuracy from 86.01% to 48.65% in the same thirty-six detection models. We also develop a list of the *TEN* most vulnerable android permissions and intents that an adversary can use to generate more adversarial applications. Later, we propose a defense strategy (*MalVPatch*) to counter the adversarial attacks on malware detection models. The *MalVPatch* defense achieves higher detection accuracy along with a drastic improvement in the adversarial robustness of malware detection models. Finally, we conclude that investigating the adversarial robustness of models is necessary before their real-world deployment and helps achieve adversarial superiority in android malware detection.

“You are what the permissions told me! Android malware detection based on hybrid tactics,”

Recent years have witnessed a significant increase in the use of Android devices in many aspects of our life. However, users can download Android apps from third-party channels, which provides numerous opportunities for malware. Attackers utilize unsolicited permissions to gain access to the sensitive private intelligence of users. Since signature-based antivirus solutions no longer meet practical needs, efficient and adaptable solutions are desperately needed, especially in new variants. As a remedy, we propose a hybrid Android malware detection approach that combines dynamic and static tactics. We firstly adopt static analysis inferring different permission usage patterns between malware and benign apps based on the machine-learning-based method. To classify the suspicious apps further, we

extract the object reference relationships from the memory heap to construct a dynamic feature base. We then present an improved state-based algorithm based on DAMBA. Experimental results on a real-world dataset of 21,708 apps show that our approach outperforms the well-known detector with 97.5% F1-measure. Besides, our system is demonstrated to resist permission abuse behaviors and obfuscation techniques.

“Metaheuristics with deep learning model for cybersecurity and Android malware detection and classification,”

Since the development of information systems during the last decade, cybersecurity has become a critical concern for many groups, organizations, and institutions. Malware applications are among the commonly used tools and tactics for perpetrating a cyberattack on Android devices, and it is becoming a challenging task to develop novel ways of identifying them. There are various malware detection models available to strengthen the Android operating system against such attacks. These malware detectors categorize the target applications based on the patterns that exist in the features present in the Android applications. As the analytics data continue to grow, they negatively affect the Android defense mechanisms. Since large numbers of unwanted features create a performance bottleneck for the detection mechanism, feature selection techniques are found to be beneficial. This work presents a Rock Hyrax Swarm Optimization with deep learning-based Android malware detection (RHSODL-AMD) model. The technique presented includes finding the Application

Programming Interfaces (API) calls and the most significant permissions, which results in effective discrimination between the good ware and malware applications. Therefore, an RHSO based feature subset selection (RHSO-FS) technique is derived to improve the classification results. In addition, the Adamax optimizer with attention recurrent autoencoder (ARAE) model is employed for Android malware detection. The experimental validation of the RHSODL-AMD technique on the Andro-AutoPsy dataset exhibits its promising performance, with a maximum accuracy of 99.05%.

“A method for automatic Android malware detection based on static analysis and deep learning,”

The computers nowadays are being replaced by the smartphones for the most of the internet users around the world, and Android is getting the most of the smartphone systems' market. This rise of the usage of smartphones generally, and the Android system specifically, leads to a strong need to effectively secure Android, as the malware developers are targeting it with sophisticated and obfuscated malware applications. Consequently, a lot of studies were performed to propose a robust method to detect and classify android malicious software (malware). Some of them were effective, some were not; with accuracy below 90%, and some of them are being outdated; using datasets that became old containing applications for old versions of Android that are rarely used today. In this paper, a new method is proposed by using static analysis and gathering as most useful features of android applications as possible,

along with two new proposed features, and then passing them to a functional API deep learning model we made. This method was implemented on a new and classified android application dataset, using 14079 malware and benign samples in total, with malware samples classified into four malware classes. Two major experiments with this dataset were implemented, one for malware detection with the dataset samples categorized into two classes as just malware and benign, the second one was made for malware detection and classification, using all the five classes of the dataset. As a result, our model overcomes the related works when using just two classes with F1-score of 99.5%. Also, high malware detection and classification performance was obtained by using the five classes, with F1-score of 97%.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

Shaukat et al. [11] devise a new DL-related method for detecting malware. It delivered superior outcomes to classical methods by merging dynamic and static analysis benefits. Firstly, it visualizes a portable executable (PE) file as coloured images. Secondly, it extracted deep features from colour images utilizing fine-tuned DL method. Thirdly, it finds malware related to the deep features of SVM. Geremias et al. [12] presented a method using image-based DL called novel multi-view Android malware identification, applied threefold. Firstly, as per the many feature sets in multi-view settings, apps were assessed, thereby raising the data presented for the classification. Secondly, the derived feature set is transformed into image formats while preserving the essential elements of data

distribution, keeping the data for the classifier task. Thirdly, built images are collectively depicted in one shot, all in a predefined image channel, allowing the implementation of DL structure.

Kim et al. [13] modelled a malware detection system called MAPAS that attains higher precision and adaptable use of computational resources. MAPAS examined the performances of malicious apps based on API call graphs of them through CNN. However, the presented MAPAS technique does not utilize a classifier method produced by CNN, it uses CNN to find typical attributes of the API call graph of malware. Fallah and Bidgoly [14] developed a technique related to LSTM for detecting malware-having the capability of differentiating benign and malware samples and identifying and detecting unseen and new types of malware. In this study, the author has executed many studies to show the abilities of the presented technique, including new malware family detection, malware identification, malware family identification, as well as assessing the minimal time needed to find malware.

Sihag et al. [15] introduced DL-based Android malware identification with the use of DYnamic features (De-LADY), a resilient obfuscation method. It has used behavioural features from dynamic analysis of an application performed in the emulated setting. Wang et al. [16] present a hybrid method related to DAE and CNN. Firstly, to enhance the precision of malware detection, the author reconstructed the high-

dimensional feature of apps and used many CNN to find Android malware. Secondly, to diminish the training period, the author used DAE as a pre-training approach for CNN. With the consolidation, DAE and CNN method (DAE-CNN) can study flexible patterns quickly.

Yadav et al. [17] presented a performance comparison of 26 existing pretrained CNN methods in Android malware detection. Depending on the outcomes, to find Android malware, an EfficientNet-B4 CNN-based approach was devised with the use of an image-based malware representation of the Android DEX file. From the malware images, EfficientNet-B4 extracted relevant attributes. Masum and Shahriar [18] devised a DL structure named Droid-NNet, for classifying malware. But this technique Droid-NNet, is a deep learner that surpasses existing cutting-edge ML approaches. Idrees et al. [19] examine PIndroid – a new Permission and Intents-based structure to detect Android malware applications. As we know, PIndroid is the primary solution, which utilizes a group of permissions and purposes supplemented with Ensemble approaches for correct malware detection. In [20], the authors establish that once the concept drift was discussed, permissions create long-lasting and effectual malware detection methods. Taha and Barukab [21] introduce a mechanism for Android malware classification utilizing optimizer ensemble learning depending on GA. The GA was utilized for optimizing the parameter settings from the RF technique for obtaining the maximum Android malware classifier accuracy. Sabanci et al. [22] intended to

categorize pepper seeds belonging to distinct cultivars with CNN techniques. Two methods are presented for classification. Initially, the CNN approaches (ResNet50 and ResNet18) are trained for pepper seeds. Secondary, diverse in the first, the features of pre-training CNN approaches are fused, and feature selection has been executed to the fused features. In [23], the authors examine recent algorithms utilized for Android Malware Detection. As a result, an outline of the Android system exposed the underlying processes and the problems facing its security structure.

Disadvantages

- The complexity of data: Most of the existing machine learning models must be able to accurately interpret large and complex datasets to detect Android Malware Detection.
- Data availability: Most machine learning models require large amounts of data to create accurate predictions. If data is unavailable in sufficient quantities, then model accuracy may suffer.
- Incorrect labeling: The existing machine learning models are only as accurate as the data trained using the input dataset. If the data has been incorrectly labeled, the model cannot make accurate predictions.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

This paper presents an Automated Android Malware Detection using Optimal Ensemble Learning Approach for Cybersecurity (AAMD-OELAC) technique. The AAMDOELAC technique performs data preprocessing at the preliminary stage. For the Android malware detection process, the AAMD-OELAC technique follows an

ensemble learning process using three ML models, namely Least Square Support Vector Machine (LS-SVM), kernel extreme learning machine (KELM), and Regularized random vector functional link neural network (RRVFLN). Finally, the hunter-prey optimization (HPO) algorithm is exploited for the optimal parameter tuning of the three DL models, and it helps accomplish improved malware detection results. To indicate the supremacy of the AAMD-OELAC approach, a comprehensive experimental analysis is carried out.

Advantages

- An intelligent AAMD-OELAC technique comprising data preprocessing, ensemble learning, and HPO-based hyperparameter tuning is presented for Android malware detection. To the best of our knowledge, the AAMD-OELAC technique never existed in the literature.
- Perform ensemble learning-based classification process comprising LS-SVM, KELM, and RRVFLN models for Android malware detection.
- The combination of the HPO algorithm and ensemble learning process improves the detection accuracy of Android malware. By utilizing multiple classifiers and optimization strategies, the model can effectively identify malicious patterns and behaviours in Android applications.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

6. IMPLEMENTATION

Modules

Service Provider

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can do some operations such as Train and Test Data Sets, View Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart, View Trained and Tested Accuracy Results, View Predicted Android Malware Detection Details, Find Predicted Android Malware Detection Ratio, Download Predicted Datasets, View Android Malware Predicted Ratio Results, View All Remote Users.

View and Authorize Users

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user's details such as, user name, email, address and admin authorizes the users.

Remote User

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user will do some operations like REGISTER AND LOGIN, PREDICT ANDROID MALWARE TYPE, VIEW YOUR PROFILE.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

In this study, we have developed the design of the AAMD-OELAC technique for an accurate and automated Android malware detection process. The intention of the AAMD-OELAC approach focused on the automatic recognition and classification of Android malware. To achieve this, the AAMD-OELAC technique encompasses data preprocessing, ensemble classification, and HPO-based parameter tuning. For the Android malware detection process, the AAMD-OELAC technique follows an ensemble learning process using three ML models namely LS-SVM, KELM, and RRVFLN. Finally, the HPO algorithm is exploited for the optimal parameter tuning of the three DL models and it helps in accomplishing improved malware detection results. To portray the supremacy of the AAMD-OELAC method, a wide-ranging experimental analysis is conducted. The simulation results portrayed the supremacy of the AAMDOELAC technique over other existing approaches.

Future work could focus on developing more advanced techniques to capture and analyze fine-grained behaviors, enabling better detection of sophisticated malware. In addition, future work could explore privacy-preserving approaches such as secure multi-party computation or federated learning, which enable collaborative malware detection without compromising user privacy.

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